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Abstract book

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Guidelines for Accelerated Partial Breast Irradiation (APBI)

Csaba Polgár

*Center of Radiotherapy, National Institute of Oncology, Budapest, Hungary
Semmelweis University, Budapest, Hungary*

In the last decades accelerated partial breast irradiation (APBI) has been intensively evaluated in prospective phase II and III clinical trials as a possible alternative to whole breast irradiation (WBI). Majority of these trials – using conservative patient selection criteria and proper treatment technique – were successful in yielding an annual local recurrence rate in the range of 0 to 1%. The long-term results of the Hungarian phase III trial and more recently the 5-year results of the GEC-ESTRO and NSABP-B39 phase III trials also demonstrated similar local control with APBI compared to WBI. Despite variability in selection criteria, the majority of women treated within these trials were >40 years old, presented with node negative invasive ductal carcinomas up to 3 cm, without extensive intraductal component (EIC), and resected with clear margins. Based on available experience international guidelines have been published by the American Brachytherapy Society (ABS), the American Society for Therapeutic Radiology and Oncology (ASTRO), and the GEC-ESTRO (Table 1.)

Table 1. International guidelines for APBI patient selection

Criterion	ABS	ASTRO	GEC-ESTRO
Age (years)	≥ 50	> 50	> 50
Tumor size (cm)	≤ 3	≤ 2 (DCIS ≤ 3)	≤ 3
Histology	All invasive subtypes and DCIS	Invasive ca. (excl. ILC) or low-risk DCIS	Invasive ca. (excl. ILC)
Margin status	Negative	Clear margin ≥ 2 mm	Clear margin ≥ 2 mm
ER status	Any	Positive	Any
LVI	Not allowed	Not allowed	Not allowed
Nodal status	pN0	pN0	pN0

DCIS: ductal carcinoma in situ; **IDC:** invasive ductal carcinoma; **ILC:** invasive lobular carcinoma; **ER:** estrogen receptor; **LVI:** lymphovascular invasion.

However controversy exists regarding the possible extension of selection criteria including patients younger than 50 years, women with invasive lobular carcinomas or DCIS, or patients with clear but close (< 2 mm) surgical margins. Ongoing clinical research actually focuses on better definition of candidates for APBI.

As data from ongoing phase III trials mature, guidelines for patient selection should be revised and might be extended. However until additional long-term outcome reports of phase III trials are available, conservative patient selection criteria (as defined by the GEC-ESTRO and ASTRO) should be considered for selecting candidates for APBI.

Keywords: APBI, selection criteria, guidelines

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